

- Supporting Information -

Impact of Carbon Corrosion and Denitrogenation on the Deactivation of Fe-N-C Catalysts in Alkaline Media

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1 **1. Experimental details**

2 **1.1 Deposition of the Fe-N-C catalyst layers**

3 The ink consisted of 11 wt% solids in 1-propanol ($\geq 99.9\%$, Sigma-Aldrich) and
4 the solid content included 70 ± 0.1 wt% the Fe-N-C catalyst (PMF-D14401, Lot 0222-
5 01B, Pajarito Powder) and 30 ∓ 0.1 wt% a commercial ionomer (AemionTM HNN5-00-
6 X, Ionomr). The ionomer was first dissolved in 1-propanol, and then this solution was
7 mixed with the catalyst powder. The resulting ink was stirred for 30 minutes, ultra-
8 sonicated for one hour (100 W, 25 ± 5 °C), and then stirred until the coating procedure.
9 With an automated film applicator (ZAA 2300, Zehntner), an ink film with a thickness of
10 $170 \mu\text{m}$ was deposited onto the gas diffusion medium while the plate temperature was at
11 30 °C. The gas diffusion electrode (GDE) – namely the catalyst layer on the gas diffusion
12 medium – was dried at 60 °C for two hours with the first hour at one atm and the second
13 hour at a reduced pressure.

14 **1.2 Analyses of the online dissolution data**

15 The gas diffusion electrode half-cell coupled to inductively coupled plasma mass
16 spectrometry (GDE-ICP-MS) has been introduced¹ and used to detect online Fe leaching
17 from realistic Fe-N-C gas diffusion electrode² in our previous works. To further regulate
18 the temperature of the GDE half-cell, the electrolyte was recirculated between the cell
19 and a heating bath (AQUAline AL25, LAUDA) to reach $T_{\text{electrolyte}}$ in the electrolyte
20 compartment, and the gas was heated up to T_{gas} by a commercial humidifier (Low Flow
21 Humidification System, Fuel Cell Technologies, Inc.) before being purged into the gas
22 compartment (see Scheme S1).

1
2 **Scheme S1.** Scheme of the gas diffusion electrode half-cell setup coupled to inductively coupled plasma
3 mass spectrometry (GDE-ICP-MS),¹ where the electrolyte in the electrolyte compartment is heated to
4 $T_{\text{electrolyte}}$ by being recirculated between the cell and a heating bath (AQUALine AL25, LAUDA), and the
5 gas is heated to T_{gas} by a commercial humidifier (Low Flow Humidification System, Fuel Cell
6 Technologies, Inc.) before being purged into the gas compartment. The Scheme is adapted from our
7 previous work,¹ which is an open access article.

8 Theoretically, the equation for the calculation of the collection efficiency (CE)^{1, 2} is
9 modified as Equation S1.

$$10 \quad CE = \frac{m_{\text{Fe,ICP-MS}}}{m_{\text{Fe,total}}} = \frac{m_{\text{Fe,ICP-MS}}}{m_{\text{Fe,bulk,end}} - m_{\text{Fe,bulk,start}} + m_{\text{Fe,ICP-MS}} + m_{\text{Fe,tube}}} \quad (\text{S1})$$

11 where $m_{\text{Fe,total}}$ is the total amount of Fe dissolved from the Fe-N-C catalyst, $m_{\text{Fe,ICP-MS}}$
12 is the total amount of Fe in the electrolyte pumped into the ICP-MS, $m_{\text{Fe,tube}}$ is the
13 amount of Fe that stayed on the inner surface of tube for the circulation of the electrolyte,
14 $m_{\text{Fe,bulk,end}}$ and $m_{\text{Fe,bulk,start}}$ are the amount of Fe in the bulk electrolyte after and
15 before each measurement, respectively.

16 However, as the Fe deposition process was also occurring during at least parts of the
17 protocol in the studied conditions, Equation S1 is not always valid for the whole protocol

1 owing to its assumption that the net flux of Fe species at the surface of the catalyst layer
 2 (CL) is from the CL to the bulk solution. Luckily, the changes in the Fe bulk
 3 concentrations are very close to those in the Fe concentration on the CL surface (see
 4 Figure S1). The CE can thus be calculated for each subprotocol using Equation S2
 5 modified from Equation S1.

$$6 \quad CE_i = \frac{m_{ICP-MS,i}}{m_{bulk,i,end} - m_{bulk,i,start} + m_{ICP-MS,i} + m_{tube,i}} \quad (S2)$$

$$7 \quad m_{bulk,i,end} - m_{bulk,i,start} = C_{bulk,i,end} \times V_{bulk,i,end} - C_{bulk,i,start} \times V_{bulk,i,start}$$

$$8 \quad \approx C_{surf,i,end} \times V_{bulk,i,end} - C_{surf,i,start} \times V_{bulk,i,start} \quad (S3)$$

9 where i refers to a certain subprotocol, such as the activity test, anodic steps or start-stop
 10 accelerated stress test (AST); $m_{ICP-MS,i}$ is the amount of Fe collected into the ICP-MS
 11 during a subprotocol; and $m_{tube,i}$ is estimated from the duration of a subprotocol and
 12 $m_{Fe,tube}$; $m_{bulk,i,end} - m_{bulk,i,start}$ is the change of the Fe content in the bulk electrolyte
 13 during a subprotocol, which can be estimated from the change of the Fe concentration on
 14 the CL surface ($C_{surf,i,end} - C_{surf,i,start}$) as explained above (see Equation S3).

15
 16 **Figure S1.** The change in the Fe concentration on the catalyst layer surface over the online measurements
 17 ($\Delta C_{CL\ surface}$) was correlated with that in the bulk solution (ΔC_{bulk}).

1 Eventually, the CEs for the measurements in O₂-HT were the average of those over the
 2 first activity test and the anodic steps subprotocols; for those in Ar-HT, we use the average
 3 of the CEs over the cathodic steps before the anodic steps and the start-stop AST
 4 subprotocols; as for those in O₂-RT, the average of the CE over the start-stop AST and
 5 the CE calculated with Equation S1 was used. The CE results are shown in Table S1.
 6 Note that two of the CE_i values were replaced with the average CE of the other four
 7 measurements (25.1%) and marked with * due to larger errors in the original values,
 8 which may be attributed to the more notable deposition process.

9 **Table S1.** The collection efficiency (CE) values for each measurement.

Sample	CE _{1st activity test}	CE _{anodic steps}	CE _{average}
O ₂ -HT-1	29.2%	27.3%	28.25%
O ₂ -HT-2	20.2%	21.35%	20.75%
	CE _{cathodic steps before anodic steps}	CE _{AST}	CE _{average}
Ar-HT-1	21.3%	30.2%	25.75%
Ar-HT-2	*25.1%	31.6%	28.35%
	CE _{S1}	CE _{AST}	CE _{average}
O ₂ -RT -1	25.3%	*25.1%	25.2%
O ₂ -RT -2	23.9%	27.4%	25.7%

10 The rate of Fe dissolution normalized with the Fe-N-C loading, $\frac{dFe}{dt} \left(\frac{pg_{Fe}}{s \times mg_{Fe-N-C}} \right)$, is
 11 calculated from the Fe dissolution raw data, [Fe] ($\mu g/L$), with Equation S4, where CEs,
 12 the Fe-N-C loadings and the flow rates of the in-situ electrolyte extraction are provided
 13 in Table S1 & S2. Also, S_{GDE} equals to 2.01 cm², the area of the GDE samples.

$$14 \quad \frac{dFe}{dt} \left(\frac{pg_{Fe}}{s \times mg_{Fe-N-C}} \right) = \frac{[Fe] \times Flow Rate}{CE \times (Loading_{Fe-N-C} \times S_{GDE})} \quad (S4)$$

15

1 **Table S2.** The Fe-N-C loadings of the GDE samples, the flow rates of electrolyte extraction, and the
 2 temperatures of the electrolyte ($T_{\text{electrolyte}}$) and the gas (T_{gas}) during the electrochemical measurements.

<i>Parameter</i>	Loading	Flow Rate	$T_{\text{electrolyte}}$	T_{gas}
<i>Unit</i>	mg·cm ⁻²	mL·min ⁻¹	°C	°C
O₂-HT-1	0.80	0.195	62.5 ± 2	60
O₂-HT-2	0.66	0.188	62.25 ± 0.25	60
Ar-HT-1	0.64	0.191	63 ± 1	60
Ar-HT-2	0.71	0.185	63 ± 1	60
O₂-RT -1	0.74	0.191	22 ± 1.5	28.5 ± 3.5
O₂-RT -2	0.67	0.188	21 ± 1	27 ± 2

3

4 **1.3 Analysis of the Fe content of the Fe-N-C catalyst powder**

5 The Fe content of the catalyst powder was measured by a PerkinElmer NexION 2000
 6 ICP-MS. Briefly, 5 mg of powders were dissolving in 1HNO₃:3HCL mixture solution (10 mL).
 7 After a digestion process using a microwave-assisted digestion system (CEM corporation), the
 8 solutions were diluted by 10 using ultrapure water (Millipore, 18.2 MΩ·cm, total organic
 9 compounds < 3 ppb). Five-point calibration curves were obtained with a blank and four
 10 prepared standard solutions: ⁵⁶Fe at 0, 2, 5, 10 and 20 μg·L⁻¹. These standard solutions were
 11 daily prepared from commercial standard mono-element ICP-MS solution (Carl Roth GmbH &
 12 co. KG, 1000 mg·L⁻¹). Rhodium (¹⁰³Rh) was used as the internal standard. To avoid any
 13 polyatomic interferences, the helium collision mode was used.

14 We obtained the Fe content in the commercial Fe-N-C catalyst powder to be 0.65 wt%.
 15 With this result, the amount of the dissolved Fe, the Fe-N-C loading in the CL, and Equation
 16 S5, we could calculate the relative loss of Fe content during a subprotocol ($-\Delta m_{\text{Fe},i}/m_{\text{Fe},0}$).

$$17 \quad \text{Relative loss of Fe content} \frac{-\Delta m_{\text{Fe},i}}{m_{\text{Fe},0}} = \frac{m_{\text{Fe,dissolved},i} \times (\text{Loading}_{\text{Fe-N-C}} \times S_{\text{GDE}})}{(\text{Loading}_{\text{Fe-N-C}} \times S_{\text{GDE}}) \times 0.65\%} \quad (\text{S5})$$

18 where $m_{\text{Fe,dissolved},i}$ refers to the amount of the dissolved Fe during a subprotocol
 19 normalized to the Fe-N-C loading. The relative loss of Fe content reported in Figure 4B is the
 20 sum of those during the anodic steps and the start-stop AST subprotocols.

1 1.4 Analysis of the electrochemical data

2 The relative losses of the capacitive charge over the start-stop AST reported in Figure 4F
3 were calculated with Equation S6.

$$4 \quad \text{Relative loss of capacitive charge} = \frac{\text{Charge}_{\text{anod. cap.,1}} - \text{Charge}_{\text{anod. cap.,200}}}{\text{Charge}_{\text{anod. cap.,1}}} \quad (\text{S6})$$

5 where $\text{Charge}_{\text{anod. cap.,}i}$ refers to the anodic capacitive charge density during the first
6 half of the i^{th} cycle, which can be calculated with Equation S7 based on the following
7 considerations. Firstly, the integral of current density with respect to time over the first
8 half of the i^{th} AST cycle ($\text{Charge}_{1^{\text{st}} \text{ half},i}$) is the sum of the anodic capacitive charge
9 density and the anodic Faradaic charge density of that cycle (see Equation S8). Figure
10 S2A illustrates $\text{Charge}_{1^{\text{st}} \text{ half},1}$ in a yellow shade and $\text{Charge}_{1^{\text{st}} \text{ half},200}$ in a red shade.
11 Secondly, the integral of current density with respect to time over the whole i^{th} AST cycle
12 ($\text{Charge}_{\text{whole cyc.,}i}$) would be approximately the oxygen reduction reaction charge
13 density during the second half of the i^{th} cycle at 0.93 V_{RHE} ($|\text{Charge}_{\text{ORR},i}|$) subtracted
14 from the anodic Faradaic charge density during the first half of the i^{th} cycle at 1.5 V_{RHE}
15 (see Equation S9). Figure S2B illustrates $\text{Charge}_{\text{whole cyc.,}1}$ in a blue shade and
16 $\text{Charge}_{\text{whole cyc.,}200}$ in a green shade. From Equations S8 and S9, Equation S7 can be
17 obtained. By integrating current density with respect to time over the 1st half of and the
18 whole i^{th} cycle (see Figure S2), $\text{Charge}_{1^{\text{st}} \text{ half},i}$ and $\text{Charge}_{\text{whole cyc.,}i}$ can be obtained.

$$19 \quad \text{Charge}_{\text{anod. cap.,}i} = \text{Charge}_{1^{\text{st}} \text{ half},i} - \text{Charge}_{\text{whole cyc.,}i} - |\text{Charge}_{\text{ORR},i}| \quad (\text{S7})$$

$$20 \quad \text{Charge}_{1^{\text{st}} \text{ half},i} = \text{Charge}_{\text{anod. cap.,}i} + \text{Charge}_{\text{anod. Faradaic},i} \quad (\text{S8})$$

$$21 \quad \text{Charge}_{\text{whole cyc.,}i} = \text{Charge}_{\text{anod. Faradaic},i} - |\text{Charge}_{\text{ORR},i}| \quad (\text{S9})$$

22 As for the contribution of $|\text{Charge}_{\text{ORR},i}|$, a maximum 6.3% difference is observed
23 between the relative losses of the capacitive charge that considers $|\text{Charge}_{\text{ORR},i}|$
24 negligible at 0.93 V_{RHE}, and that estimates $|\text{Charge}_{\text{ORR},i}|$ to be the current at the end of
25 the cycle times 3 s. And this is considered in the error bars presented in Figure 4F.

1
2 **Figure S2.** Illustration of the integrals of current density (j) with respect to time (t) over (A) the first half
3 of the 1st AST cycle (yellow shade) and the first half of the 200th AST cycle (red shade), and over (B) the
4 whole 1st AST cycle (blue shade) and the whole 200th AST cycle (green shade).

5 **1.5 Mössbauer spectroscopy**

6 A ^{57}Co : Rh source of γ -rays was used and the ^{57}Fe spectrometer (Wissel, Germany),
7 which was operated in transmission mode. The velocity driver was operated in constant
8 acceleration mode with a triangular velocity waveform. The velocity scale was calibrated
9 with the magnetically split sextet of a high-purity α -Fe foil at room temperature. For the
10 spectrum acquisition, the Fe-N-C catalyst powder was mounted in a 2 cm² holder and the
11 Mössbauer measurement was performed at 6 K in a helium flow cryostat (SHI-850 Series
12 from Janis, USA). The experimental spectrum was then fitted by a least-squares method
13 with two quadrupole doublets, with Lorentzian profiles. All the fitting parameters for each
14 doublet component were left unconstrained (relative area, IS, QS, LW). The fitted isomer
15 shift (IS) values are reported relative to α -Fe at room temperature.

16 **1.6 X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS)**

17 The XPS measurements were performed using a conventional XPS system (SPECS
18 Surface Nano Analysis, GmbH Germany) in an ultrahigh vacuum (10^{-9} mbar) analysis
19 chamber equipped with a monochromated Al K α X-ray source ($h\nu = 1486.6$ eV) and a
20 multichannel electron energy analyzer (SPECS Phoibos 150) with 1D-DLD detector.

1 High-resolution C-1s, N-1s, and O-1s core-level spectra were acquired with pass energy
2 of 20 eV and 0.05 eV step width. The measured XPS spectra were processed using the
3 KolXPD software (Kolibrík.net, Czech Republic). The fitting procedure for XPS spectra
4 involved a standard Shirley background subtraction followed by the application of a Voigt
5 function for all investigated samples. The full width at half maximum was kept constant
6 for all peaks within the same core level (1.5 for N-1s and 2 for O-1s). The element
7 contents in at% were calculated from the integrated total intensities of the C-1s, N-1s, and
8 O-1s spectra corrected by their sensitivity factors, and reported in Table S4.

9 **1.7 Raman spectroscopy**

10 A WITec alpha 300 RA confocal Raman microscope was used to acquire Raman spectra
11 of the samples. The sample was excited with a 523 nm solid-state laser at a power of 0.2
12 mW, focused on the sample surface with a ZEISS EC Epiplan-Neofluar 100x/0.9
13 objective. A WITec UHTS 300 VIS spectrometer was used to analyse the scattered light.
14 It is equipped with a Peltier-cooled, back-illuminated EMCCD camera (1600 pixels) and
15 an optical grating with 600 grooves/mm. For each sample, Raman spectra were acquired
16 at ten different positions with an integration time of 10 s. These ten spectra were averaged.
17 The fluorescent background of the samples was removed using the shape-based
18 background subtraction algorithm from the software WITec project FIVE+ at a shape size
19 of 1000.

20 **1.8 Scanning transmission electron microscopy (STEM)**

21 A Talos F200i (S)TEM from ThermoFisher Scientific equipped with a Schottky field
22 emission gun (X-FEG) and a Dual Bruker XFlash 6 | 100 EDS detector was used for
23 image acquisition. The microscope was operated at an acceleration voltage of 200 kV.
24 For high-angle annular dark field scanning TEM (HAADF-STEM) and energy dispersive
25 X-ray spectroscopy (STEM-EDXS) a beam current of 100 pA and a convergence angle

- 1 of 10.5 mrad were utilized. Selected area electron diffraction (SAED) was carried out
- 2 using an SA aperture of 10 μm at a camera length of 660 mm.

1 2. Supporting results

2 2.1 Cyclic voltammetry

3
4 **Figure S3.** A cyclic voltammetry (CV) of a pristine Fe-N-C GDE sample in Ar-saturated 0.1 M NaOH at
5 RT. The scan rate of the CV was $50 \text{ mV} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$, and the Fe-N-C loading of the sample was $0.66 \text{ mg}_{\text{Fe-N-C}} \cdot \text{cm}^{-2}$.
6 The potential data was 100% iR-corrected (80% *in situ* and 20% post iR-correction).

7 2.2 Mössbauer spectrum

8
9 **Figure S4.** The Mössbauer spectrum of the studied commercial Fe-N-C catalyst powder (PMF-D14401,
10 Pajarito Powder).

11 **Table S3.** The parameters obtained from the fitting of the Mössbauer spectrum in Figure S4, including the
12 isomer shift (IS), quadrupole splitting (QS), linewidth (LW), and relative absorption (Abs.) areas of D1 and
13 D2.

	IS mm/s	QS mm/s	LW mm/s	Abs %
D1	0.52	0.94	1.03	52
D2	0.72	2.59	1.61	48

14

1 **2.3 Online Fe dissolution data and electrochemical results (I)**

2
3 **Figure S5.** The current density (A), potential (B), and Fe dissolution rate in semi-logarithmic scale (C)
4 during the anodic steps subprotocol in O₂-RT (green) and O₂-HT (yellow) conditions.

5
6 **Figure S6.** Comparison of the online Fe dissolution from the Fe-N-C gas diffusion electrodes during six
7 40-s anodic potentiostatic holds (1.0 – 1.5 V_{RHE}) at 62 ± 2 °C (HT) in O₂ (yellow) and Ar (blue). (A, D, &
8 G) Current density profiles. (B, E, & H) Potential profiles. (C, F, & I) Fe dissolution rate normalized to
9 catalyst loading. (A, B, & C) Anodic holds at 1.0, 1.1, and 1.2 V_{RHE}. (D, E, & F) Anodic holds at 1.3 and
10 1.4 V_{RHE}. (G, H, & I) Anodic holds at 1.5 V_{RHE}.

1
2 **Figure S7.** The relative losses of Fe during the 40-s anodic steps ($-\Delta m_{Fe,E,40s}/m_{Fe,0}$) in the O₂-HT
3 (yellow), Ar-HT (blue), and O₂-RT (green) conditions.

4
5 **Figure S8.** The relative loss of the Fe content during each subprotocol ($-\Delta m_{Fe,i}/m_{Fe,0}$) in the three studied
6 conditions, O₂-RT, O₂-HT, and Ar-HT.

7
8 **Figure S9.** The increase of the overpotential at $-5 \text{ mA} \cdot \text{cm}^{-2}$ after each subprotocol in O₂ at 22°C (RT) and
9 62°C (HT) and after the whole Ar protocol at HT.

10

1 2.4 XPS spectra

2
3 **Figure S10.** XPS C-1s spectra of the pristine GDE and GDEs degraded in O₂-RT, O₂-HT, and Ar-HT
4 conditions (RT = 22 °C and HT = 62 °C).

5
6 **Figure S11.** XPS O-1s spectra of (A) the pristine GDE and GDEs degraded in (B) O₂, 22 ± 2 °C, (C) O₂,
7 62 ± 2 °C, and (D) Ar, 62 ± 2 °C conditions. The fitting peaks of O- (532.9 eV, blue, O- from H₂O,
8 hydrogen bridge bond, hydroxyls, ether, lactone, and/or carboxyls),^{3, 4} adsorbed Fe-OH bonds and/or O=
9 (531.05 eV, red, O= from carbonyls, lactone, anhydride, and/or carboxyls),³⁻⁵ C-OH and/or graphite flakes
10 (534.9 eV, purple)^{3, 6} are presented.

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Figure S12. XPS N-1s spectra of (A) the pristine GDE and GDEs degraded in (B) O₂, 22 ± 2 °C, (C) O₂, 62 ± 2 °C, and (D) Ar, 62 ± 2 °C conditions. The fitting peaks of the hydrogenated and/or protonated graphitic N (402.3 eV, blue), pyrrolic N and/or hydrogenated pyridinic N (401.1 eV, yellow), hydrogenated pyridinic N_{zigzag} surrounded by CO_x and/or pyridinic N_{armchair} neighboring COH, namely pyridonic N, (400.0 eV, purple), N bonded with Fe and/or pyridinic N (399.1 eV, green), and imine (397.5 eV, red) are presented.⁷⁻¹¹

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Figure S13. The proportion of each N species, including hydrogenated and/or protonated graphitic N ($N_{\text{hyd.gr./pro.gr.}}$ or $N_{402.3\text{eV}}$, blue), pyrrolic N and/or hydrogenated pyridinic N ($N_{\text{pyrr./hyd.pyridinic}}$ or $N_{401.1\text{eV}}$, yellow), hydrogenated pyridinic N_{zigzag} surrounded by CO_x and/or pyridinic N_{armchair} neighboring COH, namely pyridonic N, ($N_{(\text{hyd.})\text{pyridinic-CO}_x}$ or $N_{400.0\text{eV}}$, purple), Fe-coordinated N and/or pyridinic N ($N_{\text{Fe/pyridinic}}$ or $N_{399.1\text{eV}}$, green), and imine (N_{imine} or $N_{397.5\text{eV}}$, red), obtained by deconvoluting the XPS N-1s spectra of the pristine and degraded GDEs in Figure S12.

17

18

1 **Table S4.** The elemental composition in the Fe-N-C catalyst layer before (labeled as pristine) and after the
 2 O₂-RT, O₂-HT, and Ar-HT degradation protocols. The results were obtained from the XPS C-1s, N-1s, and
 3 O-1s spectra in Figure S10, S11, & S12.

Composition	C (at%)	N (at%)	O (at%)
Pristine	93.51	4.84	1.65
O ₂ -RT	91.91	4.75	3.34
O ₂ -HT	89.02	4.87	6.11
Ar-HT	89.00	4.91	6.09
Composition	C (wt%)	N (wt%)	O (wt%)
Pristine	92.26	5.58	2.17
O ₂ -RT	90.19	5.44	4.37
O ₂ -HT	86.55	5.52	7.93
Ar-HT	86.53	5.57	7.90

4

1 2.5 Raman spectra

2

3

4 **Figure S14.** Raman spectra of the pristine GDE (A, grey) and GDEs degraded in O₂-RT (B, green), O₂-HT
5 (C, yellow), and Ar-HT (D, blue) conditions. All spectra are normalized to the G peak at 1592 cm⁻¹. The
6 error range represents the standard deviation of the spectra obtained from the 10 measured spots for each
7 sample.

8 2.6 Atomic ratio of N to C

9

10 **Figure S15.** The relative increase of the atomic ratio N to C obtained from XPS N-1s and C-1s spectra in
11 Figure S12 & S10, respectively, and noted as N-1s/C-1s.

1 2.7 HAADF-STEM and STEM-EDXS results

2
3 **Figure S16.** The line profile of the arrow in Figure 5B, which provides the HAADF-STEM and EDX
4 spectrum images of powder scratched from a GDE degraded in the O₂-RT condition.

6
7 **Figure S17.** Extra HAADF-STEM and EDX spectrum images of powders scratched from (A) pristine GDE,
8 and GDEs degraded in (B) O₂-RT, (C) O₂-HT, and (D) Ar-HT conditions. Note that the magnifications of
9 (A) and (D) are the same, while those of (B) and (C) are bigger to show the features of the observed
10 depositions. The line profile of the arrow in (B) is provided in (E). The yellow dashed circles in (C) mark
11 the observed Fe/O clusters.

1
2 **Figure S18.** The upper-row images: (A) HAADF-STEM overview of particles within the powder scratched
3 from a GDE degraded in the O₂-RT condition. (B) Bright-field TEM image of the cyan-marked region in
4 (A). (C) High-resolution TEM images of an individual particle showcasing its crystal lattice. Corresponding
5 fast Fourier transformation (FFT) reveals crystal structure which is confirmed to fit to Fe₂O₃ by (D) the
6 selected area electron diffraction (SAED) pattern of the selected area shown in the inset.¹² The lower-row
7 images: (E) HAADF-STEM and EDX spectrum images of the cyan-marked region in (A).

8
9 **Table S5.** The Fe contents obtained with EDXS in pristine GDE, and GDEs degraded in O₂-RT, O₂-HT,
10 and Ar-HT conditions, in the regions without Fe particles or barely with Fe clusters.

EDS	Pristine	O ₂ -RT	O ₂ -HT	Ar-HT
Fe content (wt%)	1.015 ± 0.005	0.63	0.58 ± 0.05	0.41 ± 0.02

11

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1 **2.8 Online Fe dissolution data and electrochemical results (II)**

2
3 **Figure S19.** Comparison of the online Fe dissolution from the Fe-N-C gas diffusion electrodes during the
4 200-cycle start-stop AST in the conditions of O₂-HT (yellow) and Ar-HT (blue). (A) Potential profile. (B)
5 Fe dissolution rate normalized to catalyst loading. After the normalization, the baselines (dashed lines)
6 before the AST are shifted to 100 pg_{Fe}·s⁻¹·mg_{Fe-N-C}⁻¹ for easier comparison of the slopes of the baselines in
7 various conditions, which are positive in Ar-HT yet negative in O₂-HT. The y-axis is in logarithmic scale
8 also for easier observation of the baselines.

9
10 **Figure S20.** Comparison of the amounts of Fe dissolution from two commercial Fe-N-C catalysts (grey:
11 Pajarito Powder PMF-011904, which is Fe₃C@N-C-rich and tested in our previous work;² and green:
12 Pajarito Powder PMF-D14401, which is FeN_xC_y-rich and tested in this work) during 40-s galvanostatic
13 ORR steps in O₂-saturated 0.1 M NaOH at room temperature in the GDE half-cell. The amounts of Fe
14 dissolution were normalized to (A) the Fe-N-C loading, (B) the Fe-N-C loading and the applied electric
15 charge. The data of PMF-011904 in grey was taken from our previous work published in Journal of the
16 American Chemical Society in 2022.²

17

1 **3. Author contributions**

2 Yu-Ping Ku: GDE-ICP-MS experimental design and measurement, data curation, formal
3 analysis, scientific discussion, writing of original draft

4 Kavita Kumar: GDE-ICP-MS measurement, scientific discussion, editing

5 Andreas Hutzler: STEM measurement and data evaluation, scientific discussion, editing

6 Carina Götz: Raman spectroscopy measurement, scientific discussion, editing

7 Michael Vorochta: XPS measurement

8 Moulay Tahar Sougrati: Mössbauer spectroscopy measurement and spectrum analysis

9 Vicent Lloret: GDE high-temperature experimental design, scientific discussion, editing

10 Konrad Ehelebe: GDE-ICP-MS experimental design, scientific discussion, editing

11 Karl J. J. Mayrhofer: scientific discussion and editing

12 Simon Thiele: scientific discussion and editing

13 Ivan Khalakhan: XPS analysis, scientific discussion, editing

14 Thomas Böhm: scientific discussion and editing

15 Frédéric Jaouen: Mössbauer spectrum analysis, scientific discussion and editing

16 Serhiy Cherevko: project conceptualization and administration, validation, scientific
17 discussion, editing

18

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